

Innovation Networks of Cork, Resins and Edibles in the Mediterranean basin - INCREDIBLE

Grant Agreement number: 774632

Deliverable 3.3 – Policy recommendations on non-wood forest products

Coordination and Support Action H2020-RUR-2017-1: Thematic Networks compiling knowledge ready for practice

Start date of project: 1 November 2017

Duration of project: 42 months

Due date of deliverable: month 40 (February 2021)

Actual submission date: month 43 (May 2021)

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: FoReSTAS

Type of Deliverable: Report

Dissemination level: Public

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774632

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Contents

1. Setting the scene.....	5
2. Developing and disseminating policy recommendations for NWFP.....	6
2.1 The white paper - Collecting and prioritising policy actions for NWFP	6
2.1.1. WORKING WITHIN THE INCREDIBLE INETS.....	6
2.1.2. SOURCING INPUTS FROM OUTSIDE THE INCREDIBLE CONSORTIUM	7
2.1.3. SUMMARISING THE POLICY ACTIONS IN THE WHITE PAPER “NWFP FOR PEOPLE, NATURE AND THE GREEN ECONOMY”	8
2.2 The Policy Forum – dissemination of policy recommendations	12
2.2.1 PLANNING THE INCREDIBLE POLICY FORUM.....	12
2.2.2 THE POLICY FORUM EVENT	13
2.3 The Manifesto of Alghero – a call for action	21
3. A call on the needed policy actions	23
4. Annexes	24
Annex 1 – White paper.....	24
Annex 2 – Manifesto of Alghero	25
Annex 3 – Attendance list of the Policy Forum.....	26

Reference

Maltoni S. (2021). Policy recommendations for non-wood forest products – Deliverable 3.3. H2020 project no. 774632 RUR-2017-1 European Commission

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List of tables and figures

Table 1. Twelve key policy areas listed in the white paper “Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy”.....	9
Table 2. Further breakdown of the 12 policy areas into 27 specific policy actions.	10
Table 2 (follows) – further breakdown of policies into specific actions.....	11
Table 3. General structure of the agenda of the Policy Forum on NWFP.	14
Table 4. Detailed agenda of the Policy Forum on NWFP.	15
Figure 1. Registered participants to the Policy Forum.....	19
Figure 2. The Minister for the Environment of Portugal, chairing the Council of the European Union (first semester of 2021), highlighting the value of the white paper on NWPF.	19
Figure 3. The panellists and moderators of Session 4 of the Policy Forum.....	20
Figure 4. Sven Walter, FAO forest products officer, presents the Manifesto of Alghero, to promote action on NWFP.	21
Figure 5. Polling of actions - Question for participants; How important are the four areas of policy action in the Manifesto?	22

List of abbreviations

The following acronyms have been used across this document:

- **iNet:** innovation network
- **NWFP:** non-wood forest product
- **ToR:** terms of reference

Foreword

The INCREDIBLE project aims at leveraging knowledge transfer in the field of non-wood forest products, with a specific attention to the Mediterranean basin. One of the key tasks of the project entails filling the knowledge gaps on the *policy actions* needed to enhance the connection between innovation transfer and value chains development on the one hand, and policy measures able to tackle the challenges faced by ecosystems and economic operators on the other. This report summarises the achievements of Task 3.3 – “Policy Forum on Governance of wild non-wood forest products in Europe”, led by FoReSTAS and co-led by CESEFOR.

According to the *Description of the action*, this task has been devised to “generate policy recommendations at EU and national levels on improved governance of the collection and commercialization of edible (mushrooms nuts and berries) and non-edible (resin, cork, essential oils) non-wood forest products”. In particular “a draft document leveraging previous work will be circulated along with a bundle of relevant summarised research findings (M18) to participants in iNets dealing with edibles and to other relevant actors (from trade unions, to tourism operators, agro-industry federations etc.). A refined document will be the basis for a cross-sectoral Policy Forum to be celebrated on-line (M39). From the Policy Forum, a Policy Brief will be published in M40 (end of Task 3.3 and last element of D3.3).”

The present report a) describes the processes and methodologies followed for the development of the policy recommendations on non-wood forest products, taken from and validated at different geographical scales, from global to local; b) highlights the partnerships and collaboration agreements developed during a two-year process, and c) describes the multiple events organised to fine-tune and to leverage the findings, summarising the documents issued as final outputs of this task.

The Annexes 1 and 2 are among the main outputs of Task 3.3 and form an integral part of the present report:

- Annex 1 - The white paper entitled “*Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy. Recommendations for policy priorities in Europe. A white paper based on lessons learned from around the Mediterranean*”, has been edited and published as the fifth issue of the series *Knowledge to Action* (editors: Lukas Giessen, Sarah Adams and Inazio Martinez de Arano) of the European Forest Institute.
- Annex 2 - The “*Manifesto of Alghero: A commitment to promote the contribution of non-wood forest products to inclusive and green growth and eco-social progress in Europe and worldwide*”.

1. Setting the scene

The contribution of non-wood forest products to the sustainable development goals and the European policy agenda: In many regions of the world, non-wood forest products (NWFP) – such as cork, resins, gums, wild mushrooms, aromatic and medicinal plants, and wild nuts and berries – contribute to well-being in many different ways. They complement family income, especially in low-income households, they contribute to food security, and they are an important source of medicinal remedies. They are also part of cultural heritage and spiritual life. Being sourced from natural areas, forested landscapes and managed forests, their production and collection is intimately related with land management and biodiversity conservation. They contribute to the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, particularly to the social and cultural dimension (SDG1 - No Poverty, SDG2 - Zero Hunger, SDG3 - Health & Well-being), the environmental dimension (SDG13 - Climate Action and SDG15 - Life on Land), and to the economic dimension (SDG8 - Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure and SDG12 - Responsible Consumption and Production).

An undisclosed value: Unfortunately, for most NWFP, information on their collection, production, trade and use, remains scarce and fragmented. In Europe, the available information hints at an, as yet, unrealised potential for a rich array of NWFP. The market value of amateur NWFP collection has been estimated at €23 billion per year, most of it for self-consumption. This is in the same order of magnitude as the total value of marketed roundwood. Only a fraction of this is marketed through formal and informal channels, yet it may provide over 10% of the total income to 4.5 million households. NWFP sustain industrial value chains in cork, green chemistry, gastronomy, and pharmaceuticals, and multiply their economic impact as drivers of tourism. Just as importantly, they are intimately related with leisure, and people's relationship to nature. The current and especially the potential future economic value of NWFP largely go unnoticed in official statistics and foresight analysis, as many NWFP are part of the informal economy and not properly accounted, or are registered as agricultural products in official records.

Why developing policy recommendations? The development of policy recommendations responds to the need to recognise, and to leverage, the potential of NWFP to contribute to policy priorities in Europe, especially in relation to rural development, nature conservation, and human well-being. It shows how leveraging NWFP potential could contribute to the successful implementation of the European Green Deal, and to a greener and more sustainable post-COVID economic restart. Furthermore, realising NWFP potential could contribute significantly to achieving the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.

Gathering momentum in the current policy context: The multi-faceted importance of NWFP points towards their much greater future potential, especially when a more sustainable, fair, and nature-based development path gains political momentum, social support and market drive. Paradoxically, NWFP are generally perceived to have low economic value, overlooked in sectoral policies and even relegated to a secondary – non-wood – role in forest regulation and management practices across the continent. A number of policies are currently being drafted or in their early planning or implementation stage, that should increasingly consider the role of NWFP to contribute to their overarching objectives, just to mention a few: the EU Climate Action, the Common Agricultural Policy post 2020, the New Industrial Strategy for Europe 2020, the European Biodiversity Strategy 2020, the Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe 2020, the EU Farm to Fork Strategy, the EU Forest Strategy, and the EU action to Protect and Restore the World's Forests 2019.

2. Developing and disseminating policy recommendations for NWFP

This chapter summarises the steps carried out within the INCREDIBLE project activities, to capture the knowledge base, the expertise, the suggestions, and impulses provided within and outside the project consortium, by project partners and stakeholders of NWFP value chains originating from different sectors and backgrounds, for the definition of the *policy recommendations* on NWFP.

The findings and recommendations included in this report (and in the white paper) stem, mainly, from multi-stakeholder interactions and lessons learned from across the Mediterranean basin within the initiatives of the INCREDIBLE thematic network. Since April 2019, monthly meetings with project partners were organised by task leaders to draft and fine-tune the **Terms of**

Reference of task 3.3. This task can be broken down in two main outputs:

- Developing *policy recommendations on NWFP*, that since the early stages took up the challenge of being developed as a *White paper* on NWFP;
- Organising a *Policy Forum on NWFP* to present the policy recommendations to a wide, policy-oriented, audience.

The terms of reference (ToR) aimed at defining, for both outputs: aims and objectives, target audience, contents and scope, proposed title, index/programme, authorship/invited guests, road map for drafting. This was in parallel carried out for the contents and scope of the Policy Forum, foreseen at the end of the task 3.3. The ToR were finally approved in May 2019 by all project partners, but were progressively fine-tuned during the following months to adjust to contingency situations, with particular reference to the covid-19 pandemic outbreak.

2.1 The white paper - Collecting and prioritising policy actions for NWFP

2. 1. 1. Working within the INCREDIBLE iNets

The thematic network INCREDIBLE focusses on five distinct categories of NWFP: aromatic & medicinal plants, cork, wild mushrooms & truffles, resin, and wild nuts & berries. For each of these five categories, innovations networks (iNets) were created with the aim of fostering knowledge exchange among the actors of the value chains, both within and across sectors, and in an inter-regional dimension.

Multistakeholder interactions: The first step for developing policy recommendations was to **source the information collected in each iNet**, distilled by iNet members and coordinators. The INCREDIBLE events started for each iNet with a scoping seminar, where the value chain map was depicted together with stakeholders, a narrative was written and priorities for action were defined (Deliverable 1.3), followed by science to practice events (Deliverable 2.3), local or national meetings where practice and research representatives shared their view on topics of high interest, defined during the scoping seminars; followed by three interregional workshops per iNet (Deliverable 2.3) aiming at cross country interactions around three key topics, and by three cross-cutting innovation clinics to generate cross-pollination across sectors and iNets (Deliverables 3.1, 3.5 and 3.6). During this process and all along the project life-span relevant and ready to use information on best practices, innovations but also priorities for action were gathered in a knowledge repository and in events' reports; an open innovation challenge around successful initiatives was launched. All these events and activities, carried out within the project activities, provided a wealth of information, ready to feed into priorities for action, representing the best knowledge base for the process of collection, prioritisation and drafting of policy recommendations.

Key Policy Actions proposed and fine-tuned by the INCREDIBLE project partners: At the General Assembly held in Barcelona on 16-18 Oct 2019 an entire session was dedicated to the **submission of policy priorities by the INCREDIBLE partners and attendees to the workshop sessions**. Participants to the meeting were asked to indicate the key policy actions to be included in the white paper and to describe each action proposed in terms of: title of the key policy action, description of the action, policy area (e.g. fiscal, labour, agricultural, etc.), iNet from which the action stemmed from, best practice/case study the action referred to, further reference. A total of 28 key policy actions were submitted by the iNet members. The responses were then clustered under four key areas, which later became key subchapters of the white paper:

- Sustainable and secure supply of NWFP (subchapter 4.1);
- Securing competitive and equitable value chains (subchapter 4.2) and
- Enabling framework conditions (subchapter 4.3, later broken down in two sub chapters).

Drafting the technical working document: The actions were collected in a **technical working document**, as the basis for the white paper on NWFP. A document of over 80 pages containing the links to best practices and success cases, along with relevant policies that favour the development of NWFP value chains, was submitted in several rounds of consultations with the INCREDIBLE partners. The technical working document provided a comprehensive background for the white Paper, “EU policy priorities for the sustainability of Non-Wood Forest Products: a white paper based on lessons-learned from around the Mediterranean”. The document marks the culmination of over one-year writing work by INCREDIBLE consortium partners to distil and summarise policy actions stemming from direct stakeholders’ needs and lessons learned from across the Mediterranean basin throughout the three-year INCREDIBLE project, via interregional workshops, science to practice events, open innovation challenge and cross-cutting innovation clinics. The paper has a technical language style and references provided in the form of hyperlinks, which renders consultation unsuitable for printed copies.

2. 1. 2. Sourcing inputs from outside the INCREDIBLE consortium

Capitalising previous research findings: The policy actions summarised in the technical document also stemmed from information and recommendations provided in previous projects. INCREDIBLE aimed at capitalising previous research carried out by the Seventh Framework Programme project StarTree¹ and the COST ACTION FP1203 (European non-wood forest products network)². Several publications representing the outcomes of these projects, with particular reference to the publication *What Science Can Tell Us volume 10 “Non-wood forest products in Europe: Seeing the forest around the trees”*³. Together, these projects represent a comprehensive effort to understand and support the sustainable use of NWFP, involving several hundred researchers, practitioners, forest owners, NWFP processors, and other experts.

Welcoming FAO in the writing team: The General Assembly of Barcelona, in October 2019, was attended by Mr Sven Walter, Senior Forestry Officer and Team Leader, Forest Products and Statistics, FAO and Mr Nicolas Picard, former director of Silva Mediterranea at FAO. The FAO representatives welcomed the white paper and the Policy Forum since the early stage as two key

¹ <https://star-tree.eu>

² <https://www.nwfps.eu>

³ <https://efi.int/publications-bank/non-wood-forest-products-europe-seeing-forest-around-trees>

outputs of INCREDIBLE, in line with the expertise and work carried out by FAO on non-wood forest products in previous years and with its goals for the coming years. The FAO team in particular contributed to the review of the technical document since December 2019 through several meetings between the authors, Mr Walter and Ms Giulia Muir, to deepen the knowledge especially on issues relating to the visibility of NWFP in terms of data availability, product classification, transparency of the value chains and trade. FAO and EFI signed a cooperation agreement for the co-organization of the Policy Forum and the co-publishing of the White paper edition.

Peer review by international experts in the field of NWFP: As planned in the terms of reference of the white paper, a review process by external peers was planned, in order to benchmark the technical document with the current knowledge base and explore major gaps in the paper. Reviewers were sourced from very different backgrounds, especially with regards to the geographical span: Prof Davide Pettenella from the University of Padua, Dr Borkowsky from the European State Forest Association, Prof Chamberlain from the USDA Forest Service and Prof Eduardo Rojas from the University of Valencia. The experts, during two rounds of revisions, provided valuable suggestions for the integration of actions, references to best practices in different countries, and state of the art of the EU policy context in the technical working document.

Interactive Workshop Review by IUFRO Task force on NWFP: The technical working document also received valuable inputs from the IUFRO (International Union of Forest Research Organizations) *Task Force on Unlocking the Bioeconomy and Non-Timber Forest Products*⁴. The IUFRO-INCREDIBLE webinar occurred on 16-17 September 2020, with two sessions lasting 3 hours and 2.5 hour respectively. The sessions used Zoom breakout rooms and Miro Whiteboard to enable active discussion and comment on a 60-page technical working document. UFR0, StarTree and COST colleagues provided valuable and detailed feedback on the technical working document from which the white paper is distilled. The INCREDIBLE-IUFRO webinar welcomed participants from 14 countries and was co-organised by INCREDIBLE partners and IUFRO Task Force members, with collaboration from FAO. All attendees intervened through written proposals to improve the technical working document, which were evaluated and considered for the final version of the technical working document. Their contribution is acknowledged in the white paper.

2. 1. 3. Summarising the policy actions in the white paper “NWFP for people, nature and the green economy”

According to the project description in Annex 1 for Task 3.3 “*A refined document will be the basis for a cross-sectoral Policy Forum to be celebrated on-line*”. The “refined document” is represented by the white paper, entitled “***Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy. Recommendations for policy priorities in Europe. A white paper based on lessons learned from around the Mediterranean***”, published as the fifth issue of the *Knowledge to Action* series (editors: Lukas Giessen, Sarah Adams and Inazio Martinez de Arano) of the European Forest Institute and is available for download at the website: <https://efi.int/publications-bank/k2a>.

The white paper: Stemming from the information gathered in the technical working document, the white paper aims, through a lighter document with a policy language style, to orientate policy makers, and key economic and social players of NWFP value chains of the Mediterranean basin on the most urgent policy actions to be undertaken at the EU and national levels to untap the potential of NWFP to address the most relevant challenges in the EU agenda. It provides evidence of the relevance of NWFP beyond formal accounting, highlighting the over-riding policy loopholes

⁴ <https://www.iufro.org/science/task-forces/bioeconomy-and-non-timber-forest-products>

concerning NWFP value chains, from production, to processing and trade, and identifying the knowledge gaps on basic legal and economic information that hinder consistent and effective policy making. The white paper captures and synthesizes, in a policy language style addressed to policy makers, institutions and sectoral organizations, the key policy recommendations emerged during the review process of the technical document with all the further inputs received in the processes described above.

The white paper identifies key areas that require urgent policy attention and suggests concrete actions that could be undertaken by decision makers, key stakeholders, and societal actors at global, regional, national, and subnational scales in Europe and other parts of the world.

Based on the analysis of risks and limitations, the white paper stresses the urgent need for action and identifies promising policy options to: a) secure the conservation and sustainable supply of NWFP; b) build competitive, equitable and sustainable value chains; c) improve transparency, data and information flow on NWFP and d) establish enabling conditions in policy, financial and innovation terms (Table 1). Each of the 12 policy actions were further detailed in sub-actions (Table 2).

Table 1. Twelve key policy areas listed in the white paper “Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy”.

<p>3.1 SECURING THE CONSERVATION AND SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY OF NWFPs</p> <p>Enhance the resource base</p> <p>Ensure sustainable harvest levels and fair and secure access to the resource</p> <p>Set up and improve monitoring systems and inventories</p>	<p>3.2 BUILDING COMPETITIVE AND EQUITABLE VALUE CHAINS</p> <p>Develop innovative and territorial value chains</p> <p>Innovative fiscal and labour regimes</p> <p>Equitability and the role of producer organisations</p>
<p>3.3 TRANSPARENCY, DATA AND INFORMATION FLOW ON NWFPs</p> <p>Improve visibility of NWFPs</p> <p>Traceability and innovative labelling</p> <p>Facilitate access to data on production, commercialisation, and trade.</p>	<p>3.4 ENABLING CONDITIONS</p> <p>Coherence of institutional action</p> <p>Improve financial support</p> <p>Foster innovation, knowledge transfer and extension capacity</p>

Table 2. Further breakdown of the 12 policy areas into 27 specific policy actions.

SUPPLY

SECURE THE CONSERVATION AND SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY OF NWFP

1. Enhance the resource base

Focus on active forest management of existing forests
Embrace multi-functional forest management to enhance NWFP production
Recognise the strategic importance of agroforestry habitats
Support long-term investments into forests through appropriate instruments
Explore the role of domestication, to secure supply of most demanded NWFP

2. Ensure sustainable harvest levels and fair access to the resource

Guarantee fair, predictable and transparent access to forest resources
Regulate and respect harvest rights for NWFP
Establish adequate and realistic responsibilities and control procedures
Train workers and collectors of NWFP adequately
Build capacities on NWFP into renewed forest and agricultural advisory services

3. Set up and improve monitoring systems and inventories

Embed NWFP resource assessment in National Forest Inventories
Support resource assessment of NWFP at European, national and sub-national scales
Establish innovative procedures to record information on collection and trade
Invest in research and development of NWFP assessment and monitoring

VALUE

BUILD COMPETITIVE AND EQUITABLE VALUE CHAINS

4. Develop innovative and territorial value chains

Favour co-management of public forests
Support place-based value chains and local networks
Realise synergies with tourism in territorial development strategies
Promote new business models and downstream integration
Support certification for quality, origin and sustainability
Incorporate systems of Payments for Environmental Services

5. Design and adopt innovative fiscal and labour regimes

Define clear boundaries on who the producers are
Adopt innovative fiscal regimes
Adopt adequate labour policies to tackle seasonality and undeclared work
Contractualise the relationships between landowners and collectors

6. Strengthen equitability and the role of producer organisations

Increase transparency of price setting
Support price observatories, linked to product quality standards
Stimulate, strengthen and involve producer organisations and cooperatives

Table 2 (follows) – further breakdown of policies into specific actions

INFORM

PROVIDE TRANSPARENCY, DATA AND INFORMATION FLOW ON NWFP

7. Improve visibility of NWFP

Establish priority reporting lists for high relevance NWFP
 Improve NWFP recording in International Statistical Classifications Systems
 Integrate NWFP in individual/household consumption surveys
 Complement information by targeted sectoral and market surveys

8. Ensure traceability and encourage innovative labelling

Enforce compliance of edible NWFP with food traceability and labelling requirements
 Establish legal standards and due diligence systems
 Encourage voluntary certification and quality standards
 Inform and educate consumers through guarantee of origin
 Leverage the potential of mobile ICT solutions for labelling and traceability

9. Facilitate access to data and market information

Promote studies of costs, rents, trade, and prices for NWFP production systems
 Promote knowledge sharing through good practice guidelines and ICT platforms

ENABLE

CREATE ENABLING CONDITIONS

10. Increase policy coherence across all relevant policy domains

Work towards a consistent approach to nature and landscape conservation
 Comprehensively reveal the social and ecological dimensions of NWFP
 Support compliance with food and chemical safety regulations
 Establish a level playing field that implements circular economy approaches
 Adapt the CAP to better support NWFP conservation and development
 Develop coherent programmes for key NWFP sectors at different scales

11. Improve financial support

Define eligibility for NWFP and agroforestry land in the CAP direct payments
 Take a fresh look at rural development programmes
 Overcome barriers that prevent uptake and eligibility
 Better support NWFP within existing programmes and available funding sources

12. Foster innovation, knowledge transfer and extension capacity

Build a systemic approach to promote innovation
 Increase research attention to the social-ecological dimensions of NWFP
 Develop capacities in rural development agencies
 Strengthen forest advisory services
 Increase the attention given to NWFP in vocational training schools

2.2 The Policy Forum – dissemination of policy recommendations

Recalling once again the project declaration, whereby “*A refined document will be the basis for a cross-sectoral Policy Forum to be celebrated on-line*”, the “refined document”, represented by the white paper, formed the basis for an international and cross-sectoral Policy Forum that was celebrated on the 16th and 17th of March 2021, entitled: “*INCREDIBLE Policy Forum: Untapping the potential of non-wood forest products for Europe's green economy*”.

2.2.1 Planning the INCREDIBLE Policy Forum

According to the ToR of the Policy Forum drafted in April and approved in May 2019, the event was initially planned as an in-person event, to take place in the town of Alghero (Sardinia), organised by the partner FoReSTAS, in July 2020. Due to the covid-19 pandemic outbreak in March 2020, several project meetings occurred among partners to take into account the restrictions on movements and travel imposed at the national and European scale. A postponement of the event to late 2020 was scheduled to try to exit the period of restrictions, should the sanitary situation allow for an in-person or hybrid event. However, due to the persevering pandemic situation, the decision was finally taken by task leaders and the lead beneficiary of the project to hold a fully online event. This led to some delays in the re-drafting of the event program. The virtual mode allowed in fact, as a positive side effect, to broaden the geographical scale (international and not only European) and increased speakers’ level (more Directorate generals of the EU) and a bigger number of attendees (from initially 80 planned to 250), allowing for a greater impact on European policies and perspectives on the international dimension of NWFP values and potentials. The high relevance of the Policy Forum speakers finally achieved, including top level representatives of European and international institutions, can be considered one of the outstanding results of a concrete effort to impact European policies right at the heart of its institutions.

Concept note for the Policy Forum: NWFP such as truffles, mushrooms, wild nuts, aromatic plants or cork and resin are an often untapped source of nature-based solutions for Europe’s green economy. They provide the basis for rural economic activities and offer important sustainable alternatives to fossil-based products. Yet realising their full potential to contribute to EU Green Deal objectives and the UN Sustainable Development Goals requires joint action at European level. The Policy Forum discussed the actions needed to position NWFP as a pillar of Europe's bioeconomy. The forum was an opportunity to consider the salient issues for NWFP policies and enrich the white paper “*Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy. Policy priorities to leverage their hidden potential*”. This document stems mainly from multi-stakeholder interactions and lessons learned from across the Mediterranean basin within INCREDIBLE thematic network initiatives, the capitalization of previous research findings carried out by the FP7 project StarTree, and the COST action FP1203 NWFPs, and has received very valuable inputs from IUFFRO’s Task Force “Unlocking the Bioeconomy and Non-Timber Forest Products”. It sets out key policy messages for discussion by the Policy Forum participants to engage in action for an effective contribution of NWFP to Europe’s green economy.

Aim of the Policy Forum: The aim of the Policy Forum, which was organized as an on-line event, is to present and discuss the salient policy recommendations at the EU, national and local levels, developed through the INCREDIBLE multi-stakeholder interactions and the capitalization of previous research findings in the field of recollection and commercialisation of edible (mushrooms, nuts and berries) and non-edible (resin, cork, essential oils) NWFP. The Policy Forum provided:

- An insight into successful policy actions undertaken in countries from around the Mediterranean basin in facing those challenges.
- An opportunity to contribute to review and discuss the proposed policy recommendations.
- An opportunity to learn about the contribution of NWFP to the green economy.

- A networking opportunity with the most relevant players from the NWFP sectors and downstream value chains.
- A stage for stakeholders of NWFP value chains to describe the opportunities and challenges they face in their everyday activities.

Addressed to: The Policy Forum was addressed to EU, national, regional and local policy makers and key stakeholders in NWFP value chains (associations of forest owners, producers and processors, consumer organisations, industries, NGOs, public institutions, etc.).

Dates: 16-17 March 2021, with 4 sessions (each lasting 2 or 2.5 h).

Language: English, with translation to and from Italian for the last session.

Invited speakers: Representatives of several European institutions were invited to participate in the event, including members of the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture (DG-AGRI, DG GROW, DG ENVI) as well as experts involved in the management of European Structural and Investment Funds. Contributions from a wide range of actors helped to identify the most appropriate policies for developing and improving policy initiatives to increase the contribution of NWFP to the bioeconomy, sustainable forest management and green growth.

2.2.2 The Policy Forum event

The Policy Forum, took place on 16 and 17 March 2021, and discussed the actions needed to position NWFP as a pillar of Europe's bioeconomy. The Forum was addressed to EU, national, regional and local policy makers and key stakeholders in NWFP value chains (associations of forest owners, producers and processors, consumer organisations, industries, NGOs, public institutions, etc.). The Policy Forum was co-organised by the European Forest Institute (EFI; coordinator of the INCREDIBLE thematic network), and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), with the support of FoReSTAS (regional Forest Agency for Land and the Environment of Sardinia) and the CeseFor Foundation. This virtual event served as an opportunity to consider the salient issues for NWFP policies and enrich a white paper on policy priorities for non-wood forest products in Europe. As well, a draft of the Manifesto of Alghero was presented.

Structure of the Agenda: Table 3 summarises the general outline of the Policy Forum, providing an overview of the four sessions:

Table 3. General structure of the agenda of the Policy Forum on NWFP.

DAY 1: 16/03/2021	11.00-13.30 CET	SESSION I: Setting the scene - disclosing the potential of non-wood forest products.
	15.00-17.15 CET	SESSION II: Sustainable sourcing and secure supply of NWFP.
DAY 2: 17/03/2021	11.00-13.15 CET	SESSION III: Competitive and equitable NWFP value chains.
	15.00-17.30 CET	SESSION IV: Call for action.

Summary of aims and contents of Policy Forum sessions: the contents of each session were devised for ensuring interest of the participants and stimulating knowledge exchange on specific themes, identified as key for the development of NWFP sectors. Speakers were selected as experts or key informants drawn from the international, European and National contexts.

Session 1 aimed at “inspiring” policy makers and relevant stakeholders by showing the richness, value and diversity on NWFPs, both through the keynote and the perspectives presented by value chain operators. It is an introductory session, with an opening by hosts and politicians, and an explanation of the aim of the forum.

Session 2 aimed at describing one of the key issues that limits the potential of NWFP to contribute to SDG and Green Deal: the supply shortage and conservation of the resource. The keynote brings a global perspective, possibly remarking the concerns shared in the European context (addressed in the white paper) and gets into the details of successful actions carried out in Europe and the Mediterranean in the following round of presentations. A representative of the European Commission (DG AGRI) closes the session, to present the perspectives on the uptake of the policy actions/challenges described in the current or upcoming policy processes.

Session 3 had the same structure of Session 2, but focused on another theme/key issue: how to ensure the equitability and competitiveness of the value chains related to NWFP. The keynote provided an overview of the key challenges and opportunities in the current policy context, and on the tools to leverage the value chains. Examples of successful actions followed in the round of presentations from the operators of the value chain.

Session 4 was the conclusive session - or call for action. The white paper was presented, a final debate among international, European and national institutions discussed the relevance of the actions proposed, and the level of subsidiarity among institutions at different scales. The Manifesto on NWFP was presented to leverage engagement of participants in the claim for a greater attention to this sector.

Table 4. Detailed agenda of the Policy Forum on NWFP.

SESSION 1 - Tuesday 16 March (11.00-13.30 CET)

SESSION I: Setting the scene - disclosing the potential of non-wood forest products

High-level opening: Welcome & introductory statements

- o Marc Palahí, Director, European Forest Institute (EFI)
- o Ewald Rametsteiner, Deputy Director, Forestry Division, Food & Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)
- o Joao Pedro Matos Fernandes, Minister of the Environment and Climate Action, Portugal

A call for action to leverage non-wood forest products' potential

- o Inazio Martinez de Arano, Head of EFI Mediterranean Facility (EFIMED)

Presenting the Manifesto on NWFP

- o Sven Walter, Senior Forestry Officer and Team Leader, Forest Products and Statistics, FAO

Keynote – From Local to Global: The Enduring Power and Promise of Forest Goods

- o Patricia Shanley, People and Plants International

Perspectives from the value chains: the richness and diversity of NWFP

- o Joao Rui Ferreira, APCOR (cork)
- o Jean-Charles Savignac, Président d'honneur du Groupement européen Truffe et Trufficulture et de la Fédération française des trufficulteurs (truffles)
- o Mariana Jorge Ferreira, Luresa Resinas SL / Grupo RB (resin)
- o Jesús Quintá, president of IXP Castaña de Galicia - Alibós Galicia SL.(chestnut)
- o Hamed Daly Hassen, Ministry of Agriculture of Tunisia (aromatic and medicinal plants)

Open debate and conclusions of session I

SESSION 2 - Tuesday 16 March (15.00-17.15 CET)

SESSION II: Sustainable sourcing and secure supply of NWFP

Introduction to the session

Keynote - Sustainable Sourcing of Non-timber Forest Products: Why? What will it take?

- James Chamberlain, USDA Forest Service and IUFRO task force on non-timber forest products

Success cases for ensuring the supply of wild and semi wild forest products

- **Guaranteeing the supply of cork and the multifunctionality of *Quercus* forests**
 - Antonio Paula Soares, Chairman of the European Commission Civil Dialogue Group on “Forestry and member of the board of Confederation of European Forest Owners (CEPF)
- **Information systems on prices and producers of NWFP in Portugal (cork, resin & pine nuts)**
 - Cristina Pereira Santos, Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas (ICNF)
- **Inventory and management of wild mushrooms from EMI – examples of best practices**
 - Fernando Martínez, European Mushroom Institute
- **Voluntary standards and certification supporting sustainable and beneficial trade in wild NWFPs**
 - Anastasiya Timoshyna, TRAFFIC and IUCN Species Survival Commission - Medicinal Plant Specialist Group

Wrap-up on the needed policy actions for long term conservation and supply of NWFP

- Alvaro Picardo, Technical Adviser to the General Direction in Natural Heritage and Forest Policy of Junta de Castilla y Leon

The potential contribution of the upcoming EU policies to the development of NWFP

- Mauro Poinelli, Head of Unit “Environment, climate change, forestry and bio-economy”, Directorate-General Agriculture and Rural Development, European Commission

Open debate and conclusions of session II

SESSION 3 - Wednesday 17 March (11.00-13.15 CET)

SESSION III: Competitive and equitable NWFP value chains

Introduction to the session

Keynote - Competitive and equitable NWFP value chains, challenges and opportunities

- o Davide Pettenella, University of Padua, Italy

Success cases for fostering transparency, competitiveness and equitability of NWFP value chains:

- **The tax reform on "wild growing non-wood products" in Italy: lesson learnt and new opportunities for the forest sector**
 - o Enrico Vidale, TeSAF Department University of Padua
- **Labour and fiscal policies supporting resin holdings in Spain**
 - o Guillermo Fernández, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge of Spain
- **Ecotourism in wild mushroom sector in Greece**
 - o Vassilis Katsoupas, Kanela & Garyfallo, Vitsa Zagori, Greece
- **National Programmes for NWFPs in Turkey**
 - o İsmail Belen, Foundation of the People CARing for FUTURE (CARFU) and Ministry of Agriculture and Forests of Turkey

Key action on transparency and visibility of NWFPs

- o Giulia Muir, FAO

Wrap up on the policy actions needed to secure successful NWFP value chains

- o Sara Maltoni, FoReSTAS (Regional Forest Agency for Land and the Environment of Sardinia, Italy)

Open debate and conclusions of session III

SESSION 4 - Wednesday 17 March (15.00-17.30 CET)

SESSION IV: Call for action

Introduction to the session

The White Paper “Non-Wood Forest Products for people, nature and the green economy. Policy priorities for Europe. A white paper based on lessons learned from across the Mediterranean”

- o Inazio Martinez de Arano, Head of the European Forest Institute Mediterranean facility (EFIMED)

Panel discussion and debate: views from National, European and international institutions

- o Humberto Delgado Rosa, Director of the Natural Capital Directorate DG ENV, European Commission
- o Alessandra Stefani, General Director of the Forest Department, Italian Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry
- o Piotr Borkowsky , Executive Director of the European State Forest Association (EUSTAFOR)
- o Lyubov Polyakova , European Forestry Commission (EFC)/FAO for Europe
- o Antonio Paula Soares, Chairman of the European Commission Civil Dialogue Group on “Forestry and member of the board of Confederation of European Forest Owners (CEPF)

Bridging on future initiatives

- o Chadi Mohanna, Director of Rural Development and Natural Resources, Ministry of Agriculture of Lebanon, and Chair of Silva Mediterranea

Supporting the Manifesto on Wild and semi wild Products

- o Sven Walter, Senior Forestry Officer and Team Leader, Forest Products and Statistics, FAO

Conclusions of the Policy Forum

Number of participants to the Policy Forum and countries: Over 350 people registered to the Policy Forum (Figure 1), coming both from the public and private sector, and from different segments of the value chains (from academia to industries and policy makers). The Policy Forum was finally attended by 250 participants, including speakers and hosts, originating from 33 countries, spanning from the international provenance to the European countries. See Annex 3 for the full attendance list and the countries of origin. The event was attended with a particular interest by European countries having a great tradition and world leadership in NWFP productions and trade, such as Portugal, Spain and Italy.

Figure 1. Registered participants to the Policy Forum.

Video recordings and presentations: All video recordings of the four sessions and the presentations by speakers are available at the link: <https://www.incredibleforest.net/incredible-policy-forum>.

Figure 2. The Minister for the Environment of Portugal, chairing the Council of the European Union (first semester of 2021), highlighting the value of the white paper on NWPf.

Core messages and quotations from the Policy Forum:

“Forests are our most important terrestrial natural capital but to unlock the forest potential we need to stop looking at our forest with the old paradigm lenses, with fossil economy lenses. As a compensation for a broken economic system, we need to start using circular bioeconomy lenses and then we will see that forests are not only our most important carbon seam or the main host for biodiversity. They are also an amazing source for healthy food, biomedicine, and biological resources such as wood, cork, resins that with emerging technologies can be transformed in a total new range of bio-based solutions. So, they play a crucial role to decarbonize our economy.”

Marc Palahí, director of the European Forest Institute.

Despite all the opportunities that NWFP offer, they face significant challenges such as the lack of systematic knowledge, regulation and management, that translates in a limited political attention.

“There is a need to advance towards a common vision in the domain of NWFP and take urgent action to address those challenges.”

Inazio Martinez de Arano, head of the European Forest Institute’s Mediterranean Facility.

In this sense, experts have selected and pointed out key policy actions needed to secure successful NWFP value chains in the frame of this white paper, which are a) securing their conservation and sustainable supply; b) building competitive, equitable and sustainable value chains; c) improving transparency, data and information flow; d) and providing all enabling conditions, by ensuring coherence of the institutional action, fostering sustainable investments and improving financial support, and fostering innovation, knowledge transfer, capacity building and sharing of good practices.

“Europe has now the EU Green Deal, but the EU Green Deal will not succeed unless it engages with those managing our most important green infrastructure in Europe, which is our forests. And there is a gap in that sense. So, in my opinion, there will not be an EU Green Deal without a new deal for European forests.”

Marc Palahí, director of the European Forest Institute.

Figure 3. The panellists and moderators of Session 4 of the Policy Forum.

2.3 The Manifesto of Alghero – a call for action

The call for action developed within the white paper and presented at the Policy Forum event was further condensed in the “Manifesto of Alghero”, drawn up jointly by the participants of the Policy Forum “Untapping the potential of non-wood forest products for Europe’s green economy” and FAO.

The “**Manifesto of Alghero: A commitment to promote the contribution of non-wood forest products to inclusive and green growth and eco-social progress in Europe and worldwide**” puts forward the multifunctionality of forests, acknowledges the relevant benefits of NWFPs, the weaknesses and threats related to NWFPs, highlights the key actions to be undertaken to untap their potential and proposes different implementation strategies. Ultimately it calls for action by key national and international stakeholders.

Presenting the Manifesto: The draft of the Manifesto was launched during the Policy Forum in session 1 by Sven Walter (FAO) to get support and compromise for action among institutions, associations and enterprises, where it received suggestions for improvement and integrations, up to its final version.

Figure 4. Sven Walter, FAO forest products officer, presents the Manifesto of Alghero, to promote action on NWFP.

The Manifesto of Alghero takes the name after the town where the conference should have taken place in presence in Sardinia (Italy) and summarizes in a few pages the actions and the most relevant actors that can “take action”. The manifesto, as the white paper, is a call for policy action on different scales: to the European Commission to promote coordinated regional, national and subnational programs, improve reporting for high relevance NWFP and encourage traceability, labelling and standards for NWFP, especially valorising information about the collection and production process; to national or subnational authorities to adopt innovative fiscal and labour regimes, and implement traceability systems where appropriate; to sectoral organisations and companies to increase transparency of price setting and encourage vertical and horizontal collaboration along NWFP value chains; and to the United Nations, international organisations and academia to support countries and stakeholders to carry out the above key actions, including the collection and dissemination of data and statistics on NWFP.

The Manifesto of Alghero is available for consultation at the following link:
https://incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/u191/draft_manifesto_9.04.2021.pdf

Polling on the actions and the Manifesto of Alghero: During the Policy Forum, a polling among the participants to the event tested the interest and value of the policy actions proposed in the white paper and summarised in the manifesto. Interestingly, the four areas of policy action reached very similar scores, between 5.7 and 6 out of seven (Figure 5), showing the high relevance and complementarity of all actions for achieving the final goal of boosting NWFP value chains for the benefit of societies, economies and the environment.

Figure 5. Polling of actions - Question for participants; How important are the four areas of policy action in the Manifesto?

3. A call on the needed policy actions

A major effort in finalising the white paper and the manifesto was the endeavour to highlight the main actors in charge, or in the position of, taking action towards the implementation of successful policies for leveraging the contribution of NWFP to address the current European ambitious targets.

Policy makers (legislators) must recognise NWFPs as part of our collective heritage, as a relevant but mostly informal economic sector and as natural resources that require proper attention, coherent policy frameworks and management.

Governments can propose legislation to regulate picking and harvesting activities, labour conditions, taxation, trade, etc. to secure rights for producers and consumers, and transition towards transparent markets and knowledge-based strategic decision making.

The **European Commission** should lead the identification of the most produced/collected and consumed NWFPs in member states, clarify the production systems (e.g. farmed, semi-wild or wild products) and ensure the adequate labelling according to international standards; enhance traceability of wild food products, incorporate NWFPs to Forest Information System for Europe and to Farm Sustainability Data Network. It should also promote coordinated activities of member states through European programs for key NWFPs.

Market operators can share information and data on production/collection, processing and trade, they must respect due diligence rules when mandatory, and they can implement voluntary certification schemes to secure sustainability, traceability and fair benefit sharing.

Producers and other operators can integrate in different types of organisations (e.g., associations, cooperatives, interbranch organizations) in order to strengthen the bonds along and across value chain operators, enhancing transparency and fairness within.

Local development agencies, and agricultural and forestry advisory services must take an active role to better address NWFPs related knowledge and technology gaps, and to better support NWFP-based development opportunities.

The **research community** could better support all these efforts, enhancing coordination across countries to address relevant knowledge gaps, and support training, knowledge transfer and awareness raising activities.

NGOs can advocate, facilitate and encourage action, while **consumers** can be better informed and empower themselves to factor elements of origin, quality, sustainability and fairness in their purchase decisions.

4. Annexes

Annex 1 – White paper

The white paper “Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy. Recommendations for policy priorities in Europe. A white paper based on lessons learned from around the Mediterranean” forms the major output and an integral part of the present deliverable. It has been published as the fifth issue of the *Knowledge to Action* series and can be downloaded at the following link: <https://efi.int/publications-bank/k2a>.

The citation of the publication is:

Martínez de Arano I, Maltoni S, Picardo A, Mutke, S et al. (2021). *Non-wood forest products for people, nature and the green economy. Recommendations for policy priorities in Europe. A white paper based on lessons learned from around the Mediterranean*. EFI and FAO, Barcelona.
<https://doi.org/10.36333/k2a05>

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The publication has the following international standard book number codes:

ISBN 978-952-7426-08-1 (printed)
ISBN 978-952-7426-07-4 (pdf)
ISSN 2670-2126 (printed)

Annex 2 – Manifesto of Alghero

The Manifesto of Alghero can be downloaded at the following website for consultation:

https://incredibleforest.net/sites/default/files/u191/draft_manifesto_9.04.2021.pdf

Annex 3 – Attendance list of the Policy Forum

Pan.= panellist/speaker; Att. = attendee

User name (as provided when joining Zoom session)	Country	Session 1		Session 2		Session 3		Session 4	
		Pan.	Att.	Pan.	Att.	Pan.	Att.	Pan.	Att.
Alessandra Stefani	Italy		x		x		x	x	
Alvaro Picardo-JCyL-Spain	Spain			x				x	
Alvaro Picardo-JCyL-Spain	Spain	x				x			
Anastasiya Timoshyna/TRAFFIC	United Kingdom		x	x			x		
Antonio Paula Soares	Portugal		x	x				x	
Chadi Mohanna	Lebanon						x	x	
Cristina Pereira Santos	Portugal		x	x					
Davide Pettenella	Italy		x		x	x			x
Enrico Vidale	Italy		x		x	x			x
Ewald Rametsteiner	Italy	x							
Fernando Martínez	Spain			x					
Giulia Muir	Italy		x		x	x		x	
Guillermo Fernandez Centeno	Spain					x			
Hamed Daly Hassen	Tunisia	x							
Humberto Delgado Rosa	Portugal							x	
Inazio Martinez de Arano	Spain	x		x		x		x	
Ismail Belen	Turkey		x		x	x			x
James Chamberlain	United States of America		x	x			x		x
Jean-Charles Savignac	France	x			x		x		x
JOAO RUI FERREIRA	Portugal	x							
Lyubov Polyakova	Ukraine							x	
Marc Palahí	Finland	x							
Mariana Ferreira	Spain	x			x		x		x
Mauro Poinelli	Belgium			x					
Patricia Shanley	United States of America	x			x				
Piotr Borkowsky	Belgium						x	x	
Sven Walter	Italy	x		x		x		x	
Vassilis Katsoupas	Greece		x			x			
Vladimir Nikolić	Serbia					x			
Eduard Mauri	Spain	x				x			
Gerard Fernandez	Spain	x		x		x		x	
Raquel Castán	Spain		x		x		x		x
Riccardo Castellini	Italy	x		x		x		x	
Sara Maltoni	Italy	x		x		x		x	
Sarah Adams	Spain	x		x		x		x	
Siebe Briers - EFI	Spain		x		x		x		x
Steven Libbrecht	Belgium	x		x		x		x	
Sven Mutke	Spain		x		x		x		x

Valentino Govigli	France	x		x		x		x	
vincenzo-streppone@hotmail.com	Interpreter							x	
alessandro.tonti@outlook.com	Interpreter							x	
Abourouh	Morocco		x		x				x
Adrián E	Spain		x				x		x
Adrian Tistan - DG RTD	Belgium		x		x				
Aída Rodríguez	Spain		x		x		x		x
Alberto Negro	Italy		x				x		x
Alexandra Ricardo	Portugal		x		x				
Algis Gaižutis	Lithuania		x				x		
Almeida# Pedro	Portugal		x						
amelia	Portugal		x		x		x		x
Ana Carvalho	Portugal		x		x		x		x
ana noriega	Spain								x
Ana Paula Augusta Raposo Fernandes	Portugal		x						
Ana Teresa Belo	Portugal		x		x		x		
Ana Tomás	Portugal		x		x		x		
andrea cutini	Italy		x		x		x		
Andrea Rommeler	Germany		x		x		x		x
Ángela García de Arana - CESEFOR	Spain		x		x		x		x
Anne Stobart	United Kingdom		x						
Anthoula Efthimiou	Greece		x		x		x		x
Anton Brenko - CFRI	Croatia		x		x		x		x
Antonio De Pin	Italy		x		x		x		x
Antonio Lecegui Peregérez	Spain		x		x		x		x
António Nora	Portugal		x						
Antonio Palomeque	Spain		x				x		
APCOR Associacao Portuguesa da Cortica	Portugal		x						
Astrid van Ginkel FITOMON	Spain		x		x		x		x
Asun Roldán-Zamarrón (Tragsa Group - Innovation)	Spain		x						
Baraket	Tunisia		x						
Barbara Vinceti	Italy		x				x		
Beatriz de Torre Barrio	Spain		x		x				
Benjamin Chapelet (CNPF)	France		x		x				x
Bogdan Mihail Evulet	Romania		x		x		x		
BOYLA	Greece		x						
C Barr	United States of America		x						
Caitlin Schindler (TRAFFIC)	United Kingdom		x		x		x		x
Carmen Engong	Spain		x		x		x		
Carsten Smith-Hall	Denmark				x				
Catalan Cork Institute Foundation	Spain		x		x				
Catherine.Fournil	France				x				x
cdp5 Negrini Gabriella	Italy						x		x

Cecilia Fraccaroli	Germany			x		x		
Christophe Orazio	France	x		x		x		
Cinzia Barbieri	Italy	x				x		
Claudia Delard	Chile	x		x		x		x
Cláudia Vanessa Silva	Portugal	x		x		x		x
Clément Gonçalves	France	x		x		x		x
clizia sechi	Italy	x				x		
CM Esposende - Carlos do Carmo	Portugal	x		x		x		x
Conchi	Spain	x		x		x		x
Cristina CCM	France	x		x				
crisrina del canto	France			x				
Cristina Prades	Spain	x		x				
Cristobal GINES (NEEMO)	Spain	x						
damir akhmetshin	Ireland	x		x				
Dani Canosa	Spain	x				x		
Dasarxeio Ioanninon Rigas Tsiakiris	Greece	x						
David - Foresin	Spain	x		x		x		x
Domingos Patacho	Portugal					x		x
Dragan Čomić	Bosnia and Herzegovina	x						
Edanur Ayhan	Turkey	x		x				
ELENA BRAIDO	Italy					x		
Elisa Altomonte	Italy	x				x		x
Elise HERAL	Hungary	x		x		x		x
Emmanuel Adu-Sarpong	Germany	x				x		
Enrico Calvo	Italy	x				x		x
Eric Hoa	France	x						
Ester Blanco	Spain	x						
Fabio Boscaleri	Belgium	x		x		x		
Ferhat Yetiş	Turkey	x				x		x
Foued Aloui	Tunisia	x						
Francesca Ricardi	Belgium			x		x		
Francisco Carvalho	Portugal	x				x		
Frederico Barreira	Portugal	x		x		x		
g.stavropoulos	Greece	x				x		
Gabriella Nagy CEEweb HU	Hungary	x						
Gerhard Weiss	Austria			x		x		x
Giovanbattista Dedato	Italy	x		x		x		x
Giovanni de Alencastro	Portugal	x		x				
Giovanni Di Matteo	Italy	x				x		x
Goyo Cazurro	Spain	x		x		x		x
GPira	Italy	x		x		x		x
HENRI HUSSON CRPF NA	France	x		x				
HUSEYIN CALISKAN	Turkey	x		x		x		x
Ibtissem Taghouti	Tunisia	x		x		x		x

IGNACIO PEREDA	Portugal		x				
Ildiko Buglyo	Hungary		x		x		x
Inés	Spain		x		x		
Iñigo (Junta de Castilla y León# Spain)	Spain		x			x	
irene	Italy		x				
Iwona Piechowiak EC	Belgium					x	x
Jacobo Santos	Spain		x		x		
Jacopo Giacomoni	Italy		x		x		x
Jenne de Beer	Netherlands		x				
jeremyralph	United Kingdom		x				
Jesse Donham	Belgium		x		x		x
Jitka Menhazova	Czechia					x	
Joan Rovira_CONSORCI FORESTAL DE CATALUNYA	Spain		x		x		
Joana Paulo	Portugal		x				
João Nunes	Portugal		x		x		
João Sampaio	Portugal		x			x	x
João Silva	Portugal		x		x		
John Halley	Greece		x				
José Antonio Bonet	Spain		x		x		x
José Milheiro	Portugal		x		x		x
Judith Treis	Germany		x		x		x
Juliana Navarro Rocha	Spain		x				
Kalliopi Stara	Greece		x		x		x
Kitti Horvath	Hungary		x		x		x
Konstantina Choumi	Greece					x	
lamia Hamrouni INRGREF-Tunisia	Netherlands		x				
Laura Nocker	Italy		x				
Leonor Paiva	Portugal		x				
Lilia Infelise	Italy		x		x		x
Lilian Calaim	Portugal					x	
Luis Costa Leal	Portugal					x	
Manuel Pramsohler	Italy		x				
Margarida Tome	Portugal		x		x		x
Maria Manuel Vidal	Portugal				x		
Maria Nijnik	United Kingdom		x				
Mariaceu	Portugal		x				
Markus Spaeth	Germany		x		x		x
Marlène Baudet	France		x		x		x
Marta Iroko	Sri Lanka					x	
Marta Martins	Portugal					x	
Marta Nuero	Sri Lanka					x	
Marta Rovira	Spain		x		x		x
Matteo Rustichini	Italy		x		x		x

Meenakshi Piplani	Denmark			x			
Mehtap Koç	Turkey	x		x		x	x
Mercedes Rois	Spain			x			
Michael den Herder	Finland	x					
Michele Curel	Spain	x		x		x	x
Miguel	Spain	x				x	
Miguel Santos	Portugal	x		x			x
Miguel Segura. FETRUSE	Spain					x	
Miguel.Copete	Spain	x		x		x	x
Milos Racic	Serbia	x		x		x	
Miriam Ruiz	Spain					x	
Misun Park	Korea, Republic of	x		x			
Myrna van Leeuwen	Netherlands	x					x
Natalia Zaro	Spain	x				x	
Natalie Stryamets	Ukraine	x		x			
Nélia Aires	Portugal	x		x			x
NICKST	Bulgaria	x		x		x	x
Nicola Andrighetto	Italy	x		x		x	x
Numa Faucherre	France			x			
Nuno Ribeiro	Portugal						x
Nuno Sousa	Portugal	x					
Núria Forner	Portugal	x		x			
Olga-FAFCYLE	Spain	x					
Oliver Green	Finland					x	x
Pablo Martínez Zurimendi	Mexico	x		x		x	x
Pablo Sabin	Spain	x		x		x	
Padmini	Ghana			x			
Paola Berto	Italy			x		x	
Paula Soares (ISA)	Portugal	x		x		x	x
Petros Kakourous	Greece	x		x			
pietro oieni	Italy					x	x
Pilar Rosado	Portugal					x	x
Pino Ruiu	Italy	x		x		x	x
Polixeni Lazaridou	Greece	x					
porqueddu claudio	Italy			x		x	
Raimondo Mandis	Italy	x				x	
Raphaël Bec (CNPF)	France	x					
Raquel Puntero. Fundación Cesefor	Spain	x		x		x	x
Renaud Piazzetta - IML	France	x		x		x	x
Rita Cabana	Portugal	x					
Roberto Rubio	Spain	x				x	
Rosana López	Spain	x		x		x	
Roser	Spain			x			
rosievenn	United Kingdom	x		x			

Salaheddine Essaghi	Morocco		x					
Salvatore Seddaiu	Italy		x		x		x	
Sandra	Brazil		x		x		x	x
Sandra I Alpengummi	Austria				x		x	x
sandra pereira	Portugal		x					
Segundo(Fsc Spain)	Spain		x				x	
silvia stefanelli	Italy		x		x		x	x
simon.hrbek	Spain		x		x		x	x
simona pallanza	Italy		x					
Sofia Ferreira (FSC PT)	Portugal		x		x			x
Sónia Sanches - Dão Flora	Portugal						x	
SPYRETTA	Greece		x		x			
Stéphane PERSON	France		x		x		x	x
Stéphanie Ribeiro	Portugal		x				x	
Stephanie von Meibom	Germany		x				x	
Stephanos Diamandis	Greece		x		x		x	x
SW farmer	United States of America				x			
Sylva Koteiche	Lebanon							x
Teófilo Revenga Martinez	Spain		x					
Tiago Balsinha	Portugal		x					
Tiago Lima	Portugal		x		x		x	
TM	Spain		x				x	
Todor Stoyanov	Bulgaria		x		x			x
Ümit SERDAR	Turkey		x					
UNAC Geral	Portugal		x		x		x	x
USER	Greece		x		x		x	x
Vânia Oliveira	Portugal		x		x		x	x
Veera Tahvanainen	Belgium		x		x		x	x
Verónica Loewe	Chile				x			
violetta	Greece		x					
Willemijn de Jongh	Portugal		x		x		x	x
xananunes	Portugal				x		x	x
Ρήγας Τσακίρης	Greece				x		x	x